

Pyruvate Kinase Assay Kit Instruction

1. Principle of Measurement

2. Reagent Compositions and Preparation (50T/48 Samples)

Reagent I: 1 Bottle×60ml. Preserved at 4°C.

Reagent II: 2 Bottles of Powder. Preserved at -20°C.

Preparation of Reagent II Solution: Dissolve each bottle of powder with double distilled water (DDW) to a final volume of 1.4ml. The excess amount can be preserved at -20°C for 3-7 days. It is recommended to separate and store the solution in 2-3 tubes to avoid repeated freezing and thawing.

Reagent III: 4 Bottles of Liquid. Preserved at 4°C. Freezing is not acceptable.

Reagent IV: 4 Bottles of Powder. Preserved at -20°C.

Preparation of Reagent IV Solution: Dissolve each bottle with DDW to a final volume of 0.32ml. The excess amount can be preserved at -20°C.

Reagent V: 4 Bottles of Powder. Preserved at -20°C.

Preparation of Reagent V Solution: Dissolve each bottle with DDW to a final volume of 0.65ml. The excess amount can be preserved at -20°C.

3. Procedures

I. Pretreatment

- a. Serum Samples: Measure the sample directly.
- b. Tissue Samples: Weigh the sample precisely and add physiological saline with the ratio of 1:9 (g/ml). Homogenize the mixture and centrifuge the homogenate at 2,500 rpm for 10 min. It is accepted to dilute the supernatant acquired with saline in order to receive desirable absorbance values.

II. Procedures

Compositions (ml)	Sample	Reference (Optional)
Reagent I	1	1

Reagent II	0.05	0.05
Reagent III	0.05	0.05
Reagent IV	0.025	0.025
Reagent V	0.05	0.05
Mix thoroughly and then warm at 37°C for 10 min.		
DDW		0.02
Sample	0.02	

Record the time and add the sample simultaneously. Regulate the spectrophotometer with DDW and clean the quartz cuvette with 0.5cm path length. Record the absorbance value (A_1) of each tube 30 s after the addition of sample. After the measurement, warm the solution at 37°C and record the absorbance values (A_2) at 15 min 30 s.

Note: The reference tubes are only optional as the substance is very stable inside. Take cost into consideration and skip the reference measurement, under such circumstance, the calculation requires the absorbance value of sample tubes.

4. Calculation Formula and Example

I. Serum Sample

a. Definition

One activity unit is defined as 1 μ mol pyruvic acid generated in the presence of enzymes within 1L serum per minute at 37°C with pH=7.6.

b. Formula

$$PK \text{ Activity } \frac{U/L}{\text{Millimollar Attenuation Coefficient}^{**}} = \frac{(A_{1,Sample} - A_{2,Sample}) - (A_{1,Reference} - A_{2,Reference})^*}{15 \text{ min} \div 0.5 \text{ cm}} \times \frac{V_{total}(1.195 \text{ ml})}{V_{Sample}(0.02 \text{ ml})} \times 1000$$

Note *: Calculate only if results of reference tube are available.

Note **: Millimollar Attenuation Coefficient is 6.22 mmol⁻¹·cm⁻¹.

c. Example

0.02ml serum was prepared and measured. The absorbance values for sample tube were 0.233 and 0.225 respectively.

$$PK \text{ Activity } \frac{U/L}{\text{Millimollar Attenuation Coefficient}^{**}} = \frac{0.233 - 0.225}{6.22} \div 15 \div 0.5 \times \frac{1.195}{0.02} \times 1000 = 10.2 U/L$$

II. Tissue Sample

a. Definition

One activity unit is defined as 1 μ mol pyruvic acid generated in the presence of enzymes within proteins in 1g tissues per minute at 37°C with pH=7.6.

b. Formula

$$PK \text{ Activity} = \frac{(A_{1,Sample} - A_{2,Sample}) - (A_{1,Reference} - A_{2,Reference})^*}{U/g} \div \frac{Time}{15 \text{ min}} \div \frac{Path \text{ Length}}{0.5 \text{ cm}}$$

$$\times \frac{V_{total}(1.195 \text{ ml})}{V_{Sample}(0.02 \text{ ml})} \div \frac{C_{Protein}}{g/ml}$$

c. Example

- i. 0.05% rat hindlimb tissue homogenate was measured and the absorbance values were 0.291 and 0.210 respectively. The protein concentration of 1% homogenate was measured as 0.538mg/ml.

$$\frac{PK \text{ Activity}}{U/L} = \frac{0.291 - 0.210}{6.22} \div 15 \div 0.5 \times \frac{1.195}{0.02} \div (0.538 \div 1000 \div 20) = 3.86 \times 10^3 U/L$$

- ii. 1% rat hepatic tissue homogenate was measured and absorbance values were 0.222 and 0.156 respectively. The protein concentration of 1% homogenate was measured as 0.822mg/ml.

$$\frac{PK \text{ Activity}}{U/L} = \frac{0.222 - 0.156}{6.22} \div 15 \div 0.5 \times \frac{1.195}{0.02} \div (0.822 \div 10000) = 1.03 \times 10^2 U/L$$